

Carbazolequinone Alkaloids

HIROSHI FURUKAWA

Faculty of Pharmacy, Meijo University, Tempaku, Nagoya 468, Japan

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The first isolation of a carbazolequinone alkaloid was reported as a preliminary communication by our group¹. Only eight kinds of carbazolequinone alkaloids (Chart 1) are known to occur naturally until now²⁻⁵. This short review covers the literature on all carbazolequinone alkaloids reported to date⁶.

- 1; R₁ = R₂ = H : murrayaquinone-A
 2; R₁ = OCH₃, R₂ = prenyl : murrayaquinone-B
 3; R₁ = OCH₃, R₂ = geranyl : murrayaquinone-C
 4; R₁ = OH, R₂ = geranyl : murrayaquinone-D
 5; R₁ = OH, R₂ = prenyl : murrayaquinone-E

6. pyrayaquinone-A

- 7; R = H : pyrayaquinone-B
 8; R = prenyl : pyrayaquinone-C

prenyl:

geranyl:

Chart 1. Structure of murrayaquinones and pyrayaquinones.

Occurrence

The plants of the genus *Murraya* (Rutaceae) growing naturally in southern Asia are shrubs up to 4-5 m high⁷. Extract of the leaves and bark of this tree have been used as a folk medicine for analgesia and local anesthesia, and for the treatment of eczema, rheumatism, and dropsy⁸. The species belonging to this genus, *M. koenigii* (L.) Spreng, *M. euchrestifolia* Hayata, *M. exotica* L., and *M. siamensis* Craib, are known as a main source of carbazole alkaloids⁶. All carbazolequinone alkaloids have so far been obtained only from the root or stem barks of *M. euchrestifolia* Hayata⁷ grown in Taiwan and collected in December or May, respectively. It is of interest that the plants collected February in the same district contain only carbazoles and not any carbazolequinones.

Structure

Carbazolequinone alkaloids have a 3-methylcarbazole-1,4-quinone(1,4-dihydro-3-methylcarbazole-1,4-dione) skeleton in the molecule. Among the carbazolequinones isolated from natural sources, murrayaquinones except for murrayaquinone-A (1), have a hydroxy or a methoxy substituent at C-7

and a prenyl (C₅) or geranyl (C₁₀) side-chain at C-8 on the A-ring. On the other hand, pyrayaquinones have a 2,2-dialkylated pyran ring as an additional ring, which is biogenetically considered to be produced by the cyclisation between a prenyl or geranyl unit at C-8 (or C-6) and a free hydroxy substituent at C-7.

Structures and their spectral data (uv, ir, nmr, and mass) are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL DATA FOR CARBAZOLEQUINONE ALKALOIDS*

Murrayaquinone-A³: m.p. 246–47° (brown prisms); ¹³C nmr (24 MHz; CDCl₃+DMSO-d₆) δ 183.4s, 180.4s, 148.3s, 137.8s, 136.0s, 131.6d, 126.1d, 124.1s, 123.7d, 122.2d, 116.2s, 113.7d, 16.0q; λ_{max} (log ε) 225 (4.63), 258 (4.51), 293sh (3.85), 398 nm (3.93). ν_{max} (KBr) 1 650, 1 595, cm⁻¹; m/z 221 (M⁺, 100%), 196, 183, 168.

Murrayaquinone-B^{1,3}: m.p. 221–23° (deep purplish needles); ¹³C nmr (24 MHz; CDCl₃) δ 183.7s, 179.8s, 156.0s, 148.2s, 138.0s, 135.1s, 133.9s, 131.5d, 121.6d, 121.1d, 119.1s, 117.2s, 112.7s, 110.8d, 56.7q, 25.7q, 23.7t, 18.0q, 16.1q; λ_{max} (log ε) 210sh (4.28), 231 (4.58), 264 (4.44), 310sh (3.21), 404 nm (3.66); ν_{max} (KBr) 1655, 1640, 1610cm⁻¹; m/z 309 (M⁺, 100%), 294, 279, 278, 266, 264, 254, 241.

Murrayaquinone-C³: m.p. 158–59° (violet needles); ¹³C nmr (24 MHz; CDCl₃) δ 183.6s, 179.7s, 156.0s, 148.1s, 138.0s, 137.5s, 135.1s, 131.6s, 131.5d, 123.9d, 121.5d, 121.1d, 119.1s,

Murrayaquinone-D³: m.p. 164–68° (violet needles); λ_{max} 215sh, 234, 266, 415 nm; ν_{max} 3 440, 3 300, 1 660, 1645, 1620, 1610cm⁻¹; m/z 363 (M⁺, 100%), 313, 294, 280, 279, 278, 266, 262, 252, 241, 240, 227.

Murrayaquinone-E⁵: Brown oil; λ_{max} 232, 262, 406 nm; ν_{max} 3 430, 3 400, 1 650, 1 620 cm⁻¹; m/z 295 (M⁺), 240, 239, 149, 135.

Pyrayaquinone-A²: m.p. 222° (decomp., brown needles); λ_{max} 220sh, 252, 308sh, 460 nm; ν_{max} 3 440, 1 650, 1 610, 1 605 cm⁻¹; m/z 293 (M⁺), 278 (100%), 250, 236, 222.

Pyrayaquinone-B²: m.p. 244° (decomp., brown needles); λ_{max} 229sh, 248, 295sh, 320, 410 nm; ν_{max} 3 440, 1 640, 1 605 cm⁻¹; m/z 293 (M⁺), 278 (100%), 250, 222.

Pyrayaquinone-C²: m.p. 223° (decomp., dark-violet prisms); λ_{max} 248, 275sh, 294, 392 nm; ν_{max} 3 440, 1 640, 1 600 cm⁻¹; m/z 361 (M⁺), 346, 279, 278 (100%).

*¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were measured on 100 or 270 MHz; figures in parentheses are coupling constant (J) in Hz. Uv spectra were taken in MeOH, and ir in CHCl₃, unless otherwise stated.

Synthesis

The first synthetic approach for a naturally occurring carbazolequinone was reported in 1983¹. Since then, the synthesis of four natural carbazolequinone alkaloids have been established by five research groups. Their synthetic approaches are classified into four categories as follows.

Photooxidation of the appropriate 1-methoxy-3-methylcarbazoles :

HP 500W Hg lamp, MeOH room temp, 30 min, yield 10%¹³

125 W Hg lamp (x 2), MeOH room temp 90 min, yield 13%^{9,11}

Chart 2 *Reagents* (a) $\text{CH}_3\text{OCOCH}_2\text{N}_3$, NaOCH_3 , CH_3OH , (b) toluene, reflux, (c) CH_3I , K_2CO_3 , acetone, (d) 4-methylbutyrolactone, NaOCH_3 , dioxane, (e) H_2O , NaOH , dioxane, (f) PCC, CH_2Cl_2 , NaOCOCH_3 , (g) CH_3OH - BF_3 , (h) $h\nu$, air, CH_3OH

1-Oxygenated carbazoles are generally prepared by the Fischer-Borsche cyclisation of the appropriate cyclohexanone arylhydrazones followed by the dehydration reaction¹². Moody's group has developed a new synthetic route for 1-oxygenated carbazoles (Chart 2), one of which was derived for murrayaquinone-B (2) by photooxidation^{9,11}.

Further, they reported that the photo-oxidation of pyrayafoline-B, one of the 1-methoxy-3-methylcarbazoles having a dimethylpyran ring, resulted in its complete decomposition, and no pyrayaquinone-B (7) was isolated^{9,11}.

Oxidation of the appropriate 1- or 4-oxy-3-methylcarbazoles with Fremy's salt (potassium nitroso-disulphonate) or PCC (pyridinium chlorochromate) :

Fremy's salt [$(\text{KSO}_3)_2\text{NO}$], H_2O -acetone, room temp, 30 min, yield 40~82%^{3,10,13}
PCC, CH_2Cl_2 , room temp, several sec, yield 40%¹⁷

PCC, CH_2Cl_2 , room temp, several sec, yield 32%¹⁴

PCC, acetone, room temp, several sec, yield 30%¹⁷

Watanabe *et al.*¹³ reported the preparation of 1-hydroxy-3-methylcarbazoles through a new route by modifying the classical Fischer-Borsche method (Chart 3).

Chart 3

Miki and Hachiken¹⁵ also prepared murrayaquinone-A via Fremy's salt oxidation of 3-methyl-4-oxycarbazole (Chart 4).

Bn = benzyl, TBDMS = t-butyldimethylsilyl

Chart 4

Oxidation of the appropriate 1-oxo-3-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocarbazoles with DDQ (2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-1,4-benzoquinone) :

DDQ, dioxane, reflux, 24 h, yield 45%¹⁶

DDQ, dioxane, reflux, 12 h, yield 18%¹⁶

DDQ, dioxane, reflux, 12 h, yield 19%¹⁶

Palladium-assisted intramolecular ring closure of the corresponding 2-aryl-amino-5-methyl-1,4-benzoquinones :

The above reaction scheme is presented in Chart 5¹⁸.

Chart 5

Some analogs of naturally occurring carbazole-quinones were also prepared for synthetic and biological interests (Charts 6 and 7 respectively)^{18,19}.

Biological activities

Takeya *et al.*²⁰ found that murrayaquinone-A (1) produced a triphasic inotropic response (first positive, second negative and third positive phases)

Chart 6. Reagents : (a) PhSO_2Cl , CH_2Cl_2 , $\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+\text{HSO}_4^-$, 50% aq. NaOH , (b) CH_3ONa , CH_3OH , reflux, (c) $\text{Ce}(\text{NH}_4)_2(\text{NO}_3)_6$, CH_3CN .

- $\text{R}_1 = \text{CH}_3$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$
 $\text{R}_1 = \text{Cl}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$
 $\text{R}_1 = \text{F}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$
 $\text{R}_1 = \text{OCH}_3$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$
 $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{OCH}_3$
 $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_3 = \text{OCH}_3$
 $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_3 = \text{OH}$

- $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$
 $\text{R}_1 = \text{CH}_3$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$
 $\text{R}_1 = \text{Cl}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$
 $\text{R}_1 = \text{F}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$
 $\text{R}_1 = \text{OCH}_3$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$
 $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{OCH}_3$
 $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_3 = \text{OCH}_3$

Chart 7

of guinea-pig papillary muscle that normally paced at a slow rate of 0.2 Hz in Krebs-Henseleit solution at 30°. The effect was a concentration-dependent ($10^{-6} \text{ M} \sim 10^{-4} \text{ M}$; pD₂ value 5.27 evaluated at the first phase). The triphasic pattern of inotropism of murrayaquinone-A (**1**) was unaffected by reserpine, metoprolol or cimetidine treatment. They suggested that the effect of this quinone was not mediated through a receptor mechanism but through a novel mechanism involving mitochondrial ATP production, thereby increasing the slow inward calcium current across the cardiac cell membrane via cyclic AMP converted from mitochondrial ATP.

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